

P54 | Duration of the period from calving to fruitful insemination of cows depending on their genetic similarity to servicing bulls

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The purpose of the research was to study the interval between calving to successful insemination of cows with different genetic characteristics. The study was conducted on black-and-white holsteinized breeding cattle (*Bos taurus*). A range of microsatellite loci recommended by the International Society for Animal Genetics (ISAG) were identified in the cows and bulls (BM1824, BM2113, ETH3, ETH10, ETH225, INRA23, SPS115, TGLA53, TGLA122, TGLA126, TGLA227). Microsatellite analysis was conducted using AB 3130 genetic analyzer and the following software: Data Collection v.3.1 and GeneMapper v.4.0. The genetic similarity index in pairs “a bull – a cow” was calculated. The sampled cows were ($n = 200$) divided into three groups (I- $n=65$, II- $n=70$, III- $n=65$) according to the index of genetic similarity to the bulls: I. (≤ 0.20), II. ($0.21-0.40$), III. (≥ 0.41). The outcome of the experiment showed that the cows with the genetic similarity index below 0.2 were inseminated earlier than those with the genetic similarity index above 0.41. The interval between calving to successful insemination of the cows in group I was 143 days and in group II 163 days, in group III 198 days. The correlation ratio between the genetic similarity of the cattle pairs and the interval

between calving to successful insemination constituted $r = 0.68$ with $p \leq 0.001$. The insemination of cows by servicing bulls which do not have genetic similarity to the cows enables to reduce the duration of the period from calving to successful insemination.